

UNDERSTANDING THE CARDS

1- Front side

2- Back side

① Number and name of indicator

② Qualities of indicator

Adaptive Collaborative Empowering Legitimate Responsive

Research Methods

DESKTOP REVIEW INTERVIEW SURVEY OBSERVATION

③ Description of indicator

④ Additional information / Checklist

⑤ Checklist

#1 Coherence of existing policies

Empowering Legitimate

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are concepts in existing and proposed policies related to NbS clearly defined?
Are existing and proposed policies related to NbS written in plain language that is easy to understand?

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#2 Understandability: Complexity of rules of existing policies

Empowering Legitimate

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

NbS rules and regulations are easy to follow (for example the regulations for NbS support or subsidies) and new ones do not create obstacles and significantly delays the process of NbS implementation...

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#3 Availability: Easiness of data accessibility

Empowering Legitimate

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Does platform exist?
Is it accessible, according to principles of universal design?
Is it regularly updated?

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#4 Participation: Degree of participation

Collaborative Empowering Adaptive

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Which decision-making processes involve citizen participation and which do not? What instruments for citizen participation does the municipality employ? Where on the IAPP spectrum do existing ...

0 / 4

#5 Scientific evidence for NbS policies

Responsive

Legitimate

DESKTOP REVIEW

Was the NbS policy development process based on unbiased information and scientific research?
If so, is there transparent evidence of this?
If there is clearly documentation of the...

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#6 Credibility through transparency in evidence-based NbS policies

Collaborative Responsive

Adaptive Legitimate

DESKTOP REVIEW

SURVEY

Is the data about the procedure for policy development shared?
Is the data updated?
Do citizens know where to find the information?...

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#1 Coherence of existing policies

- Identify existing policies related to NbS
- Identify proposed policies related to NbS
- For each document, check whether key terms are defined
- Check a text sample for readability using the Flesch-Reading-Ease scoring system
- Record average scores per document
- Based on review, select documents needing improvement

#2 Understandability: Complexity of rules of existing policies

- Identify existing policies related to NbS
- Identify municipal staff involved
- Conduct interviews with municipal staff involved based on guiding questions
- Identify improvements needed

#3 Availability: Easiness of data accessibility

- Check whether platform exists
- If it exists, conduct accessibility check
- If it exists, conduct interview with website manager
- Identify areas for improvement if needed

#4 Participation: Degree of participation

- Check which departments are responsible for running public participation processes
- Where a process low on the spectrum, consider options to shift position towards 'empower' end
- Where possible, ask departments responsible for public participation to make own assessment
- For each process make a self-assessment of its place on the IAP2 participation spectrum
- Check participatory formats provided (e.g. information event, regular involvement in a council)
- Check participatory channels provided (e.g. digital survey, email/letter to politician, newsletters)

#5 Scientific evidence for NbS policies

- Identify existing policies related to NbS
- For each document, check sources of evidence provided
- For each source, check that it is publicly available
- Based on review, identify possible improvements

#6 Credibility through transparency in evidence-based NbS policies

- Identify recently completed and currently ongoing processes of policy development related to NbS.
- For each process, check how information is communicated to the public.
- Based on review, identify possible improvements.
- Survey people who live, work or use the area affected by a newly published policy
- Based on survey, identify possible improvements.

#7 Strategic stakeholder cooperation

Collaborative

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Is there a cross-departmental working group for NbS?
Is there another existing cross-departmental collaboration that could be expanded to include NbS?...

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#8 Ensuring equitable access to NbS

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

INTERVIEW

Have advocates representing minority or disadvantaged groups been invited to take part in early planning and design workshops?
Have physical, functional and perception-...

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#9 Accountability

Legitimate

Responsive

SURVEY

To what extent are you satisfied with the outcomes of this workshop? To what extent are you satisfied with the implementation of the NbS?

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#10 Different municipal departments are represented in workshops

Collaborative

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are staff from social services (e.g. neighbourhood development, public health, youth and recreation, elderly, disabilities, gender), as well as staff representing the interests of any other target groups...

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#11 Existence of designated municipal program manager who supports a specific neighbourhood in different areas

Collaborative

DESKTOP REVIEW

Was the NbS policy development process based on unbiased information and scientific research?
If so, is there transparent evidence of this?
If there is clearly documentation of the...

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#13 Accessibility to workshop

Empowering

OBSERVATION

Are participatory workshops planned, run, evaluated and continuously improved to maximise attendance and active participation from people with a diversity of interests and needs?

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- Check whether NbS working group exists
- If not, identify other existing cross-sectoral collaborations linked to NbS
- Reflect on opportunities to expand an existing collaboration or initiate a new one

- Consult stakeholder map to identify organizations representing the needs of different groups
- Review past invitations to check for inclusion of advocates to date
- Involve user groups in workshop(s) focused on needs
- Consult organisation representatives on likely access issues
- Incorporate needs in design brief

- Invite workshop participants to self-nominate for involvement in future surveys and/or interviews
- Collect survey responses from workshop participants between workshops
- Assess their satisfaction with the process and its results
- Reflect on opportunities to improve the process and/or outcome in similar future projects

- Review stakeholder map
- Consult invitation lists and attendance lists from workshops organised so far (workshop reports)
- Check departments included e.g. neighbourhood development, public health, youth, elderly, gender
- Identify any key departments missing
- Review communication strategy (WP9) for outreach approach taken so far
- Identify possible changes to engage missing departments

- Review existing strategic and organizational documents (development strategies, staff organigram)
- Identify disadvantaged neighbourhoods and responsible staff
- Conduct interview with responsible staff following guiding questions

- When planning workshops, consult Checklist for gender sensitive workshop facilitation (D1.4)
- When planning workshops, consult tips in Training toolkit for the city facilitation teams (D4.4)
- After workshops, reflect with organising team on how it went
- Review WP4 evaluation form from participants
- Identify what could be improved (use WP4 reporting template)

#14 Advocate representation for vulnerable groups

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

Have relevant vulnerable groups been identified?
Are members of vulnerable groups able to represent their own interests in workshops? If not, have organisations able to represent...

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#16 Dissemination of workshops results to participants

Legitimate

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are results shared with participants in a short, accessible format within 3 weeks of workshop?
Is full documentation made available to participants upon request?

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#17 Valuing diversity and inclusion

Collaborative

Empowering

Responsive

SURVEY

Does the municipality recognize differences between social groups and corresponding differences in needs and interests?
Are targeted communication and engagement strategies used to reach and...

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#18 Collaborative arrangements

Collaborative

Empowering

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are there multi-stakeholder partnerships supporting NbS, where the city administration works with civil society and/or private sector actors?
Who are the stakeholders involved?

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#20 Sense of employment - voice

Collaborative

Responsive

SURVEY

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are a range of instruments and channels for participation made available to citizens (e.g. online, phone number, email address, postbox in public space)?
Are these selected based on identified...

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#21 Actors commitment for NbS implementation

Collaborative

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

Do you feel that your working environment provides opportunities and incentives to develop and implement NbS initiatives?
What kind of opportunities are available?
What prevents you from engaging with th...

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- Consult organisation representatives
- Consult with colleagues responsible for social services
- Review stakeholder map and identify organisations representing minority, disadvantaged or vulnerable
- Determine whether advocates are appropriate to represent target group interests
- Consult invitation lists and attendance lists from workshops organised so far (WP4 reporting templ.)
- Identify possible changes to engage missing advocates
- Review communication strategy (WP9) for outreach approach taken so far
- Identify any key advocates missing

- Appoint 1-2 note-takers for each workshop
- Document local workshops in full.
- Develop a short, accessible summary for participants.
- Share summary with participants within 3 weeks of workshop

- Check which departments are responsible for running public participation processes
- Check which participatory channels/formats are provided (neighb. information event, workshops, etc)
- Discuss with representatives of relevant departments their own assessment of diversity in participat
- Consider what actions might help address known issues or knowledge gaps.

- Check whether one or more multi-stakeholder partnerships for initiatives related to NbS.
- If yes, those multi-stakeholder partnerships include external actors from civil society
- If yes, those multi-stakeholder partnerships include external actors from or private sector
- Reflect on the type of collaboration in place with civil society and private sector (e.g. financial
- If no collaboration related to NbS, identify other existing multi-stakeholder collaborations that ma
- Reflect on opportunities to expand an existing collaboration or initiate a new one.

- Review communication strategy (WP9) for target groups and communication channels
- After each workshop, review attendance and evaluation form responses
- Identify and improvements needed to outreach (part of workshop report)

- Check whether NbS working group exists.
- If no, identify other existing cross-departmental collaborations that may be linked to NbS
- Reflect on opportunities to expand an existing collaboration or initiate a new one

#25 Acceptance and uptake

Adaptive

Legitimate

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are NbS considered by different actors (i.e., municipal officials, politicians, NGOs, housing developers) a viable solution for your city's development?
Does NbS explicitly feature in strategic pla...

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#26 Objectives sharedness among stakeholders

Collaborative

SURVEY

To what extent do you feel your ideas, interests or goals were taken into account in the objectives defined for the NbS?
To what extent do you feel you have contributed to the NbS design...

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#30 Knowledge sharing: environmental education

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

How many and which kind of environmental education activities are carried out in a year in your city?
Who is involved in education campaigns (number and type of actors)?

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#31 Broad consensus and understanding for shared vision

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

INTERVIEW

Is the process of collectively developing a strong shared vision related to NbS based on broad and diverse participation? Exists a broad consensus on general goals, challenges, and concerns, as well as on...

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#32 Capacity-building of local actors

Collaborative

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

SURVEY

Does training in care for the NbS take place?
How is training opportunity promoted?
How many participants?
How is training evaluated by participants?
What proportion of participants apply thei...

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#37 Easy-to-reach intermediate actions

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

INTERVIEW

The NbS policy development process was based on clear and easy to reach intermediate targets?
If so, which actors /staff are involved in their achievement? Have they worked collaboratively?...

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- Review existing strategic plan
- Identify actors involved (e.g. municipal officials, politicians, NGOs, housing developers)
- Identify if NbS explicitly feature as option for city's development
- If possible identify which actors push for their uptake

- Invite workshop participants to self-nominate for involvement in future surveys and/or interviews
- Survey returning workshop participants to gather perceptions of own satisfaction w/ process & outcome
- Based on responses, reflect on opportunities to improve the process and/or outcome in similar future

- Check whether a database exists reporting the events organized by the municipality
- Count the trainings, education and/or awareness actions implemented in the past year
- Identify the type of actors involved (see stakeholder mapping)
- Count number and type of attendees in trainings, education and/or awareness actions in last year
- Consider strategies to make more education opportunities available

- Invite workshop participants to self-nominate for involvement in future surveys and/or interviews
- Survey returning workshop participants in between workshops to gather perceptions of own satisfaction
- Based on responses, reflect on opport. to improve the process/ outcome in similar future projects

- Check if training in caring for the NbS is offered to community members
- Review number of participants taking part in training
- Evaluate participant satisfaction with training through survey
- Review number of trained participants applying skills to the NbS
- Compare number of trainees with participants actually applying skills
- Reflect on any areas of improvement needed

- Review existing strategic and organisational documents (e.g. development strategies)
- Identify if intermediate targets are set for their achievement
- Identify the actors/staff involved in their achievement
- Interview involved staff following the guiding questions
- Based on review, identify possible improvements

#38 Empowering through co-creation process

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

Do you feel you were involved in the co-creation process? Do you feel empowered and having voice in the co-creation process?

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#39 Fair treatment of people across time without bias and favouritism

Legitimate

SURVEY

To what extent do you consider the organising party/decision-maker was impartial during the process?
To what extent do you consider the organising party/decision-maker was hone...

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#40 Inclusion of direct day-to-day-management of green spaces in the (planning) process

Responsive

Adaptive

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are the actors involved in the day-to-day management of green spaces involved in the NbS planning process?

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#41 Integration of environmental and social agendas at all levels

Responsive

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Do the environmental agendas (e.g. aims, plans projects) consider the social impact, and vice versa?
Do the actors in environmental and social agendas actively exchange and collaborate...

🗳️ 0 / 7

#42 Knowledge brokers

Empowering

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are there any individuals or organizations supporting participants in their learning processes related to NbS issues? Are they translating different forms of knowledge and knowledge claims?

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#43 Linking environmental understanding with values of local actors

Responsive

SURVEY

Are your (ecological) values reflected in the information provided?

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#38 Empowering through co-creation process

- Invite workshop participants to self-nominate for involvement in future surveys and/or interviews
- Survey returning workshop participants in between workshops to gather perceptions of own satisfaction
- Based on responses, reflect on opport. to improve the process /outcome in similar future projects

#39 Fair treatment of people across time without bias and favouritism

- Invite workshop participants to self-nominate for involvement in future surveys and/or interviews
- Collect survey responses from workshop participants between workshops
- Assess their satisfaction with the process and its results
- Reflect on opportunities to improve the process and/or outcome in similar future projects

#40 Inclusion of direct day-to-day-management of green spaces in the (planning) process

- Check whether NbS working group exists
- If not, identify other existing cross-sectoral collaborations linked to NbS
- Identify if actors involved in the day-to-day NbS management are involved
- Conduct survey with municipal staff and local partitioners
- Reflect on opportunities to expand an existing collaboration or initiate a new one

#41 Integration of environmental and social agendas at all levels

- Check whether NbS working group exists
- If not, identify other existing cross-sectoral collaborations linked to NbS
- Identify if actors in environmental and social agendas are involved
- If yes assess if their agendas are aligned or integrated in NbS
- If yes identify on which NbS governance level/ levels
- Conduct interview based with municipal staff involved in environmental and social agendas
- Reflect on the difficulties and possible improvements

#42 Knowledge brokers

- Consult invitation lists and attendance lists from workshops organised so far
- Check if anyone supporting participants in their learning processes on NbS issues has been involved
- Reflect on whether their involvement has facilitated participants' learning processes
- Reflect on whether their involvement helped translate participants' knowledge and knowledge claims

#43 Linking environmental understanding with values of local actors

- Invite workshop participants to self-nominate for involvement in future surveys and/or interviews
- Collect survey responses from workshop participants between workshops
- Assess their satisfaction with the process and its results
- Reflect on opportunities to improve the process and/or outcome in similar future projects

#45 Political or institutional support

Collaborative

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

What is the organizational structure planning, implementing and managing NbS? Is it hinders or support NbS planning, implementation and management?

🗒️ 0 / 4

#50 Process-oriented approach

Adaptive

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Is a process-oriented instead of a project oriented approach applied? Is the city employing standards, personnel, capacities, rules, internal guidelines, and KPIs in guiding the process and not only for the...

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#52 Openness about uncertainties

Adaptive

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are uncertainties are acknowledged and openly discussed? Are uncertainties communicated? Are uncertainties acknowledge in the learning process?

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#53 Attention for local conditions

Responsive

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are capacities, culture, values, socio-economic conditions, environmental situation, political conditions taken into account in the design, planning and management of NbS?

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#54 Evaluation of group dynamics and power imbalances

Empowering

Legitimate

OBSERVATION

Have any perceived power imbalances been identified by the workshop participants?
Have any perceived power imbalances been identified by the workshop organizers?
Have any perceived power imbalances...

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#55 Identification and involvement of diverse and vulnerable group of key actors representing different sectors

Collaborative

Empowering

Responsive

Legitimate

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Is there a broad and fair representation of stakeholders? From which sectors and how many stakeholders are involved?

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- Identify the organizational structure planning, implementing and managing NbS (staff organigram)
- Identify other existing cross-departmental collaborations linked to NbS
- Conduct interview with identified members (municipal staff and/or local practitioners)
- Reflect on how it supports or hinders the planning and implementation of NbS

- Identify and review existing strategic documents
- Identify the organizational structure planning, implementing, managing NbS (e.g. staff organigram)
- It is a well-defined processes: based on standards, personnel, capacities, rules, guidelines, KPIs
- Is strategic: focuses on process to reach set goals and visions and not on set goals and visions & its goals and visions are fuzzy and evolving and can be re-assessed
- Is incremental: consists of different steps including planned and unplanned actions & asks for regular evaluation to identify new strategies
- Is participatory: engages different actors and to determine what is mutually acceptable
- It embeds integral and continuous learning
- Its planning is non-linear and in frequent need of revision

- Identify strategic and organisational documents (e.g. development strategies, staff organigram)
 - Consult the involved colleagues
- Assess if in the planning process of NbS uncertainties are:
- Identified
 - Estimated
 - Communicated
 - Assess if accounting for uncertainties provide potentials to learn from

- Identify and review existing strategic documents (e.g. development strategies)
- Identify organizational structure planning, implementing and managing NbS (e.g. staff organigram)
- Consult the involved staff
- Reflect if informal arrangements/rules co-exist with formal procedures in decision-making process
- Identify the unwritten rules / knowledge that enters decision-making recognised as legitimate
- Identify embedded/exogenous conditions influencing decisions (e.g. climatic conditions, economy)
- Reflect on opportunities for improvements

- Check WP4 evaluation forms to monitor perceived power imbalances reported by participants
- Check WP4 reporting template for monitoring workshop organizers' observations on power imbalances
- Identify whether any power imbalances have been recognized by the participants
- Identify whether any power imbalances have been recognized by the organizers
- Compare the development of perceptions of power imbalances over time

- Consult stakeholder map to identify high-interest / low-influence stakeholders
- Consult invitation lists and attendance lists from workshops organised so far
- Count number of high-interest / low-influence stakeholders involved and relative sector
- Identify their sector
- Interview representatives from different sectors
- Identify best engagement strategies

#56 Governance ICT maturity: knowledge representation

Responsive

INTERVIEW

Is the data presented in a clear, accessible, actionable, user-friendly, unbiased, and comprehensive manner?
Do the visualizations, tables, and published data align with established benchmarks?

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#57 Co-governance transaction costs: data processing

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

On average, how many person-days is spent on processing 100 citizen's led initiatives?

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#59 Participation volume

Responsive

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

How many comments, proposals, ideas, feedback does the city receive related to NbS on an annual basis?

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#60 Lifecycle participation gap

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are citizens contributing throughout the whole lifecycle of NbS projects?
How those contributions, initiatives, and feedback are distributed in the project life-cycle phases?

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#61 User journey participation gap

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

Do some citizen fall out of participating in certain phases of the project?

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#62 Representativeness of participants

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

Does the socioeconomic and spatial composition of participants represent those affected by the project?

☑ 0 / 7

#56 Governance ICT maturity: knowledge representation

Conduct interview with municipal staff from ICT department inquiring the following points:

- Check whether a data governance protocol is used
- If yes, report the followed standard
- If not, identify the industry standard you'll be using as a benchmark
- Gather a representative sample of data representations (e.g. graphs, tables, published data document)
- Compare each data representation against the industry standard you've defined
- Create a scale of maturity levels (e.g., low, moderate, high)
- Apply the scale of maturity levels to each data representation
- Interpret the results and identify patterns, strengths, and areas for improvement

#57 Co-governance transaction costs: data processing

- Identify staff involved in processing citizen's led initiatives (e.g. events, trainings, workshop)
- Ask staff involved to estimate the time needed to process ONE initiative
- Compute average time
- Multiply average time (if in minutes divide by 60) per 100 citizen contributions
- Divide the resulting number of hours by your full-time equivalent working day (in hour)

#59 Participation volume

- Identify how citizens contribute, send feedback and propose initiatives in your the municipality
- List how (e.g., council committee meetings, emails, approaching council members)
- If other departments involved consult your colleagues to collect their inputs
- Count number of received NbS feedback per year
- Write here the result: ...

#60 Lifecycle participation gap

- Identify how citizens contribute, send feedback and propose initiatives in your the municipality
- If other departments involved in NbS consult your colleagues to collect their inputs
- Count the number of direct and indirect citizen contributions per year
- Associate each contribution to the design, planning, implementation or management phase
- Reflect on the life cycle phases in which contributions are low

#61 User journey participation gap

- Identify how citizens contribute, send feedback and propose initiatives in your the municipality
- Create social group labels in consultation with equal opportunities departments to represent most
- If other departments involved in NbS consult your colleagues to collect their inputs
- Count the number of direct and indirect citizen participation per year
- Associate each contribution to the design, planning, implementation or management phase
- Associate each contribution to relevant social group labels
- Compare the presence and share of each social group in different phases

#62 Representativeness of participants

- Specify a sample of ongoing or finished NbS-related projects, legislation, policies in the last 5 year
- Identify how citizens contribute, send feedback and propose initiatives associated with these projec
- Create social group labels in consultation with equal opportunities departments for representation
- Count the number of direct and indirect citizen participation per year
- Associate each contribution with neighb. of the contributor, the project/policy item, & social grps
- Inquire from the project managers and engaged stakeholders the target groups and affected parties
- Compare target groups composition with composition of contribution per project/policy

#63 Governance ICT maturity: knowledge production

Responsive

INTERVIEW

Are there enough capacities and tools to transform raw data and information into actionable insights with added value to justify the collection of the data?

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#64 Knowledge dissemination reach

Collaborative

DESKTOP REVIEW

How effective are communication channels in reaching and engaging citizens?

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#68 Bottom-up initiatives: volume

Responsive

DESKTOP REVIEW

How active are citizens in launching initiatives?

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#75 Instruments of consent

Legitimate

INTERVIEW

DESKTOP REVIEW

Are citizens able to give, decline, and retroactively decline consent to projects influencing their right to ecological space under justifiable conditions and without unreasonable effort?

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#76 Fidelity of representation

Legitimate

INTERVIEW

What mechanisms regulates digital identity, data ownership, and stakeholder agency in the A.I. lifecycle?
Do citizens know and have a say in how they are represented in decision-support systems?

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Conduct interview with municipal staff from ICT department inquiring the following points:

- There is enough staff to process the acquired data (structured information from a variety of sources)

The data acquired enable to produce actionable synthesis in the following context:

- Knowledge producing technologies focus on mapping impacts
- Knowledge producing technologies focus on untangling interactions in social-ecological-
- Knowledge producing technologies integrate tacit knowledges of different social groups
- Knowledge producing technologies focus on dynamic/process information
- Knowledge producing technologies help to translate policy/stakeholder objectives
- Reflect of possible improvements

- List communication channels posts/activities of last year (e.g., social media, webpage, email)
- Count number of passive engagement for posts/activities (i.e., visits, reads, views, observations)
- Count number of active engagements for posts/activities (i.e., comments, shares, participation)
- Sum number active passive engagements, divided per month times 100000 (qty/(m*100000 pop))

- Check whether a citizen-led events database exists
- If no, identify the department that issues the permit to organize citizen-led events
- Count the number of citizen-led initiatives in the last 5 years
- Divided the number of citizen-led initiatives per year times 100000 (qty/(a*100000 pop))

- Specify a sample of 2/3 ongoing or finished NbS-related projects in the last 5 years
- Conduct interview with municipal staff from ICT department inquiring the following points:
- Identify published information (e.g., monitoring data, health implications, distribution of impacts)
- Assess if the information provided enable citizens to make autonomous decisions
- Identify how those information are provided (e.g., searchable databases, visual, media coverage)
- Assess if information is provided for inquiring non-gov actors after the project completion
- Identify if and how citizens are able to give, decline, and retroactively decline consent
- Reflect on the ease of finding information for personal decision-making without unreasonable effort
- Reflect on 'maturity' of consent-giving practices and options for improvement

- Reflect on citizens capacity to judge, instruct, recall their digital representations and interests
- Identify your data and A.I. governance framework (apart from EU GDPR regulation)
- Identify if mechanisms to exercise ownership rights over certain data generated exist
- Identify what kind of information representing one's viewpoint, symbols / GIS maps semantics
- Identify digital identity management (e.g. digital identification, detail asked, anonymity)
- Conduct interview with municipal staff from ICT department inquiring the following points: